

Roman empire expansion dynamics from 338 BC to 116 AD

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Abstract. A lot of ancient civilizations has risen and fallen again, namely a few as Roman empire, Macedonia kingdom, Inca Empire, etc. To date many interesting and already available facts are known about ancient empires, but not much about their evolutionary dynamics,- for example their timeline of population or occupied area in a world. Using carefully selected information sources, in this paper I try to represent how Roman empire size has changed over time with quantitative metrics from 338 BC to 116 AD.

Using already compiled Roman empire occupied territory maps by Prof. H. M. Wiseman¹, I was able to extract Roman empire size in an arbitrary units (pixels occupied in a world map picture) and draw this ownership of territory over time in a chart, which is below :

X axis represents years elapsed from 338 BC, which is right after a birth of Roman empire core. Y axis is the size of Roman empire as measured in pixel amount in a compiled map, which by territory belongs to Romans. Red line is an exponential model of Roman empire growth, which expressed by equation would be :

$$A = A_0 e^{\alpha t} \quad (1)$$

Where A_0 is initial Roman empire size at 0 timeline point (at 338 BC in absolute time units); α is empire growth rate, which happens to be about 0.0134;

¹<https://howardwiseman.me/Roman/19Maps.html>

t is elapsed years. Current exponential fit to empirical data has qualitative feature of $R^2 = 0.95$, which shows that data fit is quite good. It's worth to note, that I have already tried to fit data points using a power-law instead, but that has a bit smaller confidence level, $R^2 = 0.93$, so in my opinion exponential fit is a bit more accurate.

Conclusions. Roman empire growth in a period 338 BC to 116 AD can be modelled using exponential fit (1), which quite good represents theoretical empire growth in these years. As an interesting side-note the term “Blitzkrieg” or a “Quick warfare” coined in WWII by German military forces may not be something new not known before to ancient generals and armies. As my chart shows Roman occupation of vast territories in just 450 years may represent a quick war (“Blitzkrieg”) for that time, because owned territories grows exponentially ! In my opinion every exponential territory growth can be called a “Quick warfare” (Blitzkrieg). One may not agree with this view and comparison of Roman empire expansion dynamics to “true Blitzkrieg’s” performed by axis in WWII. But think that, Romans didn’t had such warfare advancements like axis had (armored vehicles and quick transport, air support, etc). Even information between Roman army units was exchanged by several orders of magnitude slower (no radio support, just horses, etc). Given that and mentioned exponential conquering of territories it’s correct to name Roman warfare tactics as some form of Blitzkrieg.

Further research ideas:

1. It would be interesting to check if some other war-related territory ownership expansions follows an exponential law, like ancient Macedonia kingdom growth, WWII axis-owned territories growth, etc.

2. It’s a known fact that many of great ancient civilizations has gone extinct at least in a form which they existed before (same Roman empire at maximum peak of wealth for example). The thing that great ancient civilizations are prone to collapse and dis-integration *may be* related to the very fact of their exponential growth, which in the end produces some instabilities. This is just a unverified hypothesis, which needs a moderate amount of research. However, we may have some facts which indirectly may support this idea. Think about some form of exponential growth of human body mass, which ends-up in a death finally. Or think about virus colonies, which after a quick expansion, dies rapidly when food resources are depleted. Even our universe is subject to dis-integration (Big Rip scenario) if it will grow exponentially in the future. A link between an exponential growth and collapse/dis-integration or produced instabilities should be a very interesting research topic.